

Positive And Negative Thinking Aspects And Its Relationship To The Personality Type (Optimistic - Pessimistic)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 25 ,2023</p> <p>Accepted: January 28, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Thinking, (Positive - Negative), Personality, (Positive - Negative).</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10619681</p>	<p><i>The present study aims at identifying the determiners of thinking (positive-negative) and their relation to the (Optimistic-Pessimistic) personality as well as the differences between the variants of the sample according to the gender (males-females), specialization (pure sciences- humanistic sciences) ,and grade of studying (second-fourth). The sample of the study includes (400) students, both males and females from the University of Al-Qadisia for the academic year (2018-2017). The present study has adopted two scales: the scale of thinking determiners which includes (36) items, and the scale of traits of personality which includes (32) items. The researcher set both of these scales off. The results of the study have shown that (84.5%) of the sample are optimistic and (15.5%) pessimistic. It has been also noticed that there is no significant difference on the statistical bases in the determiners of thinking and the Traits of personality according to the variants that have been already mentioned. Moreover, it has been concluded that there is correlation between the determiners of thinking and the traits of personality. In the light of these results, the researcher has proposed some recommendations and suggestions.</i></p>

Introduction

The problem and the aim of the present study lie in presenting a theoretical framework about the determiners of positive and negative thinking for the students of university and their relation to the traits of optimistic and pessimistic personalities especially under the current circumstances that are experienced by the university students who suffer because of the economic and social difficulties out of wars and Terrorism. These circumstances have affected, in a way or another, the determiners of their thinking, leaving several problems, which are reflected on the present, as well as the future of the students. Their social and academic adaption, on one hand, and the society on the other, became hopeless and disappointed. As a result, they became unable to face the conflicting changes, which made them suffering the loneliness and meaninglessness. This has led to a negative impact on the continuity of their education as well as their capabilities inside and outside the university. The hard living circumstances, caused by the successive crises that have serious repercussions on the cognition, values, and ethics, made it difficult to stick to the positive moral and social values. The college students at the present who are living under such trouble situation, just like the whole society, are having a transitional state which made their lives filled with continuous problems and conflicts in family and university in specific and in the society in general. These might lead them to the negative thinking. Thus, identifying the determiners of thinking patterns as well as their characteristics among the students would lead to know the generations that would bear the responsibility of building the future of this society. Moreover, this would help to improve the methods of teaching to be suitable in a way that serve and participate in giving the students the skills of the positive thinking. Therefore, the problem of the present study is identified as a try to answer the following questions:

- Identify the determiners of thinking (Positive-Negative), traits of personality (optimistic–pessimistic) of college students.
- Are there significant differences in determiners of thinking, and the traits of personality, and is there an effect according to the variables: gender, specialization, and studying grade?
- Is there a relationship between the determiners of thinking and traits of personality for the college students?

The study of the college students' personality, in its variable dimensions, represents extreme importance in the field of psychology. The academic compatibility, thinking about the future and planning it, and the social and economic problems, which affect the psychological balance of the students, lead to psychological crises. These crises would distract their energies to do their roles effectively. On the other hand, the positive thinking and the optimistic personality are reflected on the behavior of individuals, their social relations, and the psychological and physical health. The optimistic person expects goodness, joy, and success. He would also be able to achieve a psychological and social compatibility. Moreover, his creativity and problem solving would be more active. In addition, positivity optimism help the student to classify and order the information which would lead to increase their success in their studying, identify their goals, and follow certain methods to overcome their problems. Thus, it is important for those who are concerned with educating the college students to know the extent of the availability of these traits of the normal personality, on one

hand, and the availability of a tool to measure these traits, on the other. This might enable them to know the way in which their students act toward the future problems, the goals that they want to achieve, the techniques of reducing the negative thinking, and the suitable circumstances to grow the positive personalities of the students.

Determinants of Thinking (Positive - Negative)

The human nervous system is very complex and adapted in a way that serves its variable needs. It also organizes the biological processes, which are required for being alive on a regular basis and in high harmony. This device could be considered as the basic element of the function integration of the human being. The human mind does complex processes like thinking, remembering, awareness, learning, expectation, and concluding in addition to the biological and physiological processes which are necessary to keep the body active and effective (through the regulation and coordination with the other parts of the body like the joints, muscles, and glands). The former mental processes work through senses stimulation, which is related, with the external stimulators.

Thinking is a continuous series of specific notions that is stimulated by a particular inquiry, which is in need of a solution of a specific kind. It includes internal processes for the elements of the stance, on one hand, and prepares the individual for the internal stimulators that he has. Thus, thinking is based on two mental processes: induction and deduction, which differentiate the man from the other living creatures. Developing this characteristic requires intensive efforts. Some individuals think in a negative way to the extent that they find out some defects even in the positive things. Therefore, many scholars think that the thinking method, whether positive or negative, is an innate process founded in the human being from childhood, but the positive thinking is a skill that could be learned and mastered in a way that it be the direction for happiness and success in the whole life regardless of his status and/or education. The nature of the brain is that it could be trained on goodness and be able to acquire organized, deep, and creative thinking[1].

The positive thinking suggests the effectiveness in maintaining the right balance of recognizing the various problems. It is an integrated way of life, which means focusing on the positives of any stance instead of the negatives. It includes the positive idea about the self and others. The positive mood is reflected on his behavior and his interpretation for the various issues. Negative thinking, on the other hand, is a group of negative thoughts, which are used by the individual to convince himself about the situations and events. It also refers to a sense of incapability, failure, and unpopularity and so on in an endless list of negative feelings and thoughts. The negative feelings might start by an experience such as a failed action or exam. Instead of getting advantage of that experience, he generalizes it all over his life. This effect of that experience is renewed in each future issue. The reality of the negative thinking is much more dangerous than it appears since it makes the life as a continuous series of troubles and bad feelings and behaviors. This would lead to negative results like psychological and biological illness, and to feel alone, scared, and lost which are the result of conjecture, exaggeration, or the pressure of problems. It also leads to discomfort and anxiety. There are several reasons that could be a strong motivation to generate negative thinking (Frank, 2004; Sharma, 2004; Whyte, 2004; Patterson, 2003; Tincher, 2003; Bhatnagar, 2003). These are represented as follows:

- **Partial View of Events:** it refers to the superficial and narrow view for the matters. It is considered as a minor thinking and/or misunderstanding or perception. Such an individual evaluates all the people around him according to the side that he understood or thought about it.
- **Temporal Stairs:** the focus is done on a specific period, which is usually a recent one. This mode of thinking remains momentary and does not care about the future.
- **Egocentrism:** this thinking is centered on what is achieved by the individual as personal interests, in the sense that the perception and thinking are characterized as being selfish and lacks the notion of "total social". Moreover, he follows the sentimental feelings and effects in addition to the exaggeration of these affective stances without a deep vision or self-confidence.
- **Arrogance:** it refers to the individual's sense of arrogance and showing-off in his way of thinking. It is considered as one of the common errors in the thinking of people, which might lead the person to exaggerate things to give himself an excuse.
- **First Impression:** it is one of the phenomena of the thinking that is based on a misunderstanding. This type of thinking is characterized as being impulsive and hasty in taking a decision about a certain issue without having a deep thinking or examining. Thus, the individual should be able to correct his image of the outside world that is created through his first impression when he discovers that he was wrong.
- **Extremism:** it is the individual's desire to launch generalized and radical expressions both positive and negative. This is considered as one of the obstacles to the way of positive thinking, since the individual's thinking is being based on the overgeneralization through assessing a part or aspect. Such people usually use decisive linguistic expressions, which would not accept any modification or correction. So that, it leads to certain behaviors which would affect his relationships with others.
- **Absence of goals:** it indicates the lack of any Utopian or great goal in the individual's life. Such individuals usually lack high ambitions, which might cause an intellectual emptiness.
- **Judgment Trends:** it means the lack of sound objective standards, which identify the right impression about things; so that the individual's decisions would be based on a shallow vision descended from his/her feelings, emotions, and the

psychological and social trends, which are irrational and unconvincing. The result is that they commit errors, and fail in their awareness and thinking.

- Halo Effect: It indicates the idea of being effected in the present judgment of behavioral phenomenon by the already knowledge about it. Thus, if his idea or knowledge were positive, his evaluation would be affected even if it is negative and vice versa (his/her already negative idea would effect on the evaluation even if it were positive at this time).
- Prior Patterns: Sometimes, the individual use in his judgment and evaluation prior stances so that s/he be effected by the general characteristics both the positive and negative of these already taken stances. The problem here is that the thinking is characterized as being generalized. This generalization might be wrong because the individual differences cannot be generalized in our judgment and ignore these differences[2].
- Socialization and its Challenges: The process of socialization faces two types of challenges: the first one is internal i.e. it is descended from the society itself, its rules, and its measurements. The second one is external in a way that its sources flow from outside the society that is represented by the variables that go into its culture through the negative and/or positive interaction. Socialization in the traditional societies used to be limited to some educational and social foundations like family, school, and mosque. These support each other in order to achieve sound upbringing away from contradiction and compaction among their objectives.
- The wars: perhaps the famous saying in this issue is that the big fish make the wars and the small ones are the victims. This expresses the extent of the morale and psychological impact of wars on children. Many psychological studies and researches confirm the dangerous impacts of wars that appear on children in terms of losing the psychological balance, the emergence of many psychological problem, severe anxiety and panic and misery. According to Na'ema Al-Badrawi, a specialist in psychological and psychiatric medicine, the traumas that the children got by the humans' hands are much harder than those of the natural disasters and longer termed in memory[3].
- It becomes much more difficult if these traumas were repeated with some unpleasing experiences in frequent intervals. The accumulation of these experiences for children and youth would be in the form of deep psychological and psychological problems especially when the family of society fail to overcome such problems. The most important problems that are caused by wars are Malnutrition, disease, displacement, orphaning, calamities because of violent viewing, and commit acts of violence, disability and dependency.
- Domestic climate: the family is considered as the strongest external factors that affect the formation of an individual's personality. It controls and orients his/her behavior. From the family, the one takes his /her experiences, customs, and traditions as well as identifies the right and wrong. There is no organization or institution can affect the person more than the family especially at the early stages of his/her life.
- School: The school is a social and educational institution that conduct teaching and education together as it does to do jobs that are almost contradictory: transfer heritage and maintain it, and change the present and keep up with evolution. Only the good educational system is the one that can reconcile both sides. School has established when societies evolved and knowledge became complicated and variable. The family became unable to afford these functions alone. Thus, most societies started to provide their members with official educational institutions to teach them the various kinds of knowledge. Despite the fact that school had rubbed many tasks from the traditional educational institutions, it cannot replace them in any way. Thus, these institutions remain working parallels with school. The most important kind of these institutions is the family[1].
- Individual's sense of inadequacy and inferiority: This is considered as one of the vital factors that could affect the patterns and styles of thinking.

Personality Traits (optimistic – pessimistic)

Personality is considered as one of the important subjects in the psychological field in all its patterns, characteristics, and transformations. It is the overall concept of the human self both outwardly and inwardly with all his/her inclinations, visions, beliefs, and convictions. The definitions of the notions of optimism and pessimism are subjects of debate among psychologists. This made the mission of the psychologists very difficult especially those who are interested in the study of personality in order to give an acceptable theoretical framework. Some looked at them as elements of personality while other looked at them as two of the general traits or bipolar traits. These two traits affect the individual's behavior, his/her socialization, and his/her physical and psychological health. The optimistic person expects goodness, joy, and success. He would also be able to achieve a psychological and social compatibility. While the pessimist expects evil, despair, and failure. S/he looks at life negatively and tend to use what I called "pessimistic interpretation" which means the personal interpretation of negative events. This leads us to say that the matter is related to the way the individual be aware of the different events and stances. The psychologists of personality look at these traits as being general themes surrounding the psychological status of individuals. They affect the determiners of thinking of the present and future[4] have given another meaning for the trait of optimism. They defined it as being the individual's personal readiness to expect what is positive toward the events of life for the present and future. On the other hand,[5] have presented an explanation for pessimism according to the nature of individual's feeling. They pointed to the hidden positive hopes and expectations in the tries for change and the continuous failure in the way of dealing with the social environment and as a result, s/he feels that s/he is a negative outcome of this environment. These traits could be learned

and gained from the environment and experience. This make it easy to modify them to be patterns supporting the personality of the individual rather than frustrating pattern[6].

- Some elements are supposed to determine the degree of individuals in the traits of personality (optimistic-pessimistic). These include:
 1. School ingredient: if the school elements, including the teachers and administrators, were optimistic, this would be reflected on their students' personalities and the way of choosing their friends.
 2. Family ingredient: the general atmosphere of the family, the way of child rearing, and the planting of values and beliefs would form the personality of the child and make him/her either optimistic or pessimistic. The individual who faces a series of difficult or sudden situations would tend to be pessimistic and vice versa. These elements aid in the process of forming the pessimism and optimism in the personality.
 3. Economic ingredient: Reseal (1989) Indicated that the ongoing economic downturn undoubtedly affected the life goals set by the college students for their professional future. Due to the vague future, it is expected that the students would develop new directions based on such dire circumstances as well as set some plans for their life especially in the area of work. This undoubtedly would affect the average of optimism and pessimism [7].
 4. Social ingredient: Each society hold a special character of being characterized as optimistic or pessimistic concerning the economic and technological circumstances, which are upgraded and renewed. Media has a tremendous effect on the formation of the emotions of individuals and direct them toward optimism and pessimism. The social ingredient is represented by the socialization that help the individual to acquire language and traditions and habits of his society. It is expected that social ingredient has a vital role in optimism and pessimism especially between the two sexes in our society. The males have a big space to express their opinions, which generate high self-esteem, positivity, hope, and optimism toward future. They own the decision in determining their fate. Females, on the other hand, have much less chance because of the customs and traditions, but this does not mean that females have no optimism. The general atmosphere of the family, the way of education, and planting values, ethics, security, and self-confidence would polish the personality of the individual and make it either optimistic or pessimistic.
 5. Political ingredient: conflicts and wars result crisis and psychopathological problems. Moreover, the exploitation of technology and sophisticated inventions is devoted toward the domination of certain sates on others that cause destruction to the human race, and the civil-cultural elements of the societies. Such problems would cause sentimental isolation, emotional poverty, sense of emptiness of life, and loss of psychological balance. These lead to many psychological conflicts, which soon become behavioral aspects like fear from the future, pessimism, and loss of hope [8].
 6. Health ingredient: the optimism and pessimism of the individual affect his health. The optimistic person is free of anxiety, stress, and depression. This would help him/her to acquire a positive fine heath[9]. On the contrary, the bad heath causes and strengthen the negative thinking. Thus, the person would live in a negative environment as that the challenges of life would be bigger so that his/her life would be a series of troubles. Having negative fiends in their thoughts and visions also focus the attention on negativity and make the mind opens all similar negative files that also cause similar results. The negative thinking makes the individual comfortable with those who support his negative opinions.
 7. Biological ingredient: it includes the genetic qualities and inherited characteristics. Some researchers assumed that these determiners have a role in optimism and pessimism. A study (Plomin,elat,2006) on a sample of (500) people of identical twins has shown that heredity has an important role in the traits of optimism and pessimism. It has the share of (25%) of the personality. The heredity and environment are working together in this process(Muheisen,2012). The following are the most important features that characterize the optimistic and pessimistic personality. Traits of optimistic personality: the optimistic personality is characterized of having the following traits and features:
 1. Physical features: these include the way of standing, walking, sitting, and sleeping of an individual. The optimistic personality is characterized as being relatively relax psychologically. Concerning the facial expressions, it could be easily noted that the optimistic person smiles a lot with sense of hope. His looks would not be sharp, false, and dispersed when you speak to him. S/he would not move his/her eyebrows during the conversation. S/he does not think with a loud, and his/her voice is free of turmoil and instability, frequency. S/he tends to be normal concerning his/her eating habits and, has deep sleeping that is free of nightmares.
 2. Affective features: the optimistic person characterized as having stable emotional balance that last for a long period relatively. S/he does not be happy or sad because of vague or no reasons. In addition, s/he is capable to be pleased with the little. S/he expects the positive things and does not expect that s/he would cry. The optimist responds emotionally to the feelings and emotions of others, spread the positive energy among others, and does not enclosed on him/herself. She tends to the bright colors and simplicity.
 3. Mental features: S/he acquires good mental patterns and correct information. S/he tends to take acceptable stances and s/he gets rid of bad mental patterns and wrong thinking. S/he looks at the matters from the others point of view rather than his/her own. Moreover, his/her mind is characterized as being dynamic. It has the ability to add and delete as

well as checking up his thoughts from time to time. Such people believe that they will have better future both as individuals and/or as groups.

4. Verbal features: His/ her speech is filled with satisfaction, success, and positivity. S/he uses some words that give hope and comfort for others as well as the tendency to report good news that are related to the others like success and happy occasions to encourage them.

5. Social features: the first and most feature of the optimist socially is being reassured to the others in general. S/he does not expect evilness from the others and S/he does not find a contradiction between his and their success. Moreover, S/he participates in building up the new generations on the hope that it would be better than the previous ones. Also, S/he does not measure him/herself with others from one angle like the pessimist does and S/he respects the humanistic personality and S/he hopes that the wisdom of humanity would win in the general and political issues both in the present and future.

Methodology and procedures

- The subject of the study: it consists of the college's students of the second and fourth stages /University of Al-Qadisia for the academic year (2018-2017). They are (2719) male students, and (2573) female students. They were classified according to gender, specialization, and stage.
- Sample of the study: The present study is conducted on a sample of (400) college students/ University of Al-Qadisia and they were chosen according to the Prepositional Allocation.

Instruments

- The researcher has used Positive and Negative Thinking Scale (PNTS) which is set by the researcher himself after surveying the theoretical framework and some previous studies like (Anthony, 2002), (Blunden, 2004), (Haveren, 2004). The scale composed of (36) items that were constructed according to the five-alternatives of Likert (I Always agree, I agree very much, I agree sometimes, I rarely agree, I do not agree). The total score of this scale ranging (36-180). The high score indicates positive thinking while the low score refers to the negative thinking. The score (108) is adopted to be the borderline between the positive and negative thinking.

- The researcher, also, has used the scale of the traits of personality (optimistic and pessimistic) after a survey of theoretical literature and previous studies (Al-Ansari, 2005) (Barakat, 1998), and (Khalil 2009) as well as some scales like (Demner, et al, 1989) (Al-Hakak 2001) (Seligman, 1995), and (Al-Humairi, 2003). In the light of these, a scale was developed to collect the data from the samples. This scale aims at measuring the traits of personality (optimistic and pessimistic) in the college students. It includes (32) items, which were constructed in two directions: the positive and negative distributed in six fields. These fields are school ingredient, family ingredient, economic ingredient, social ingredient, political ingredient, and health ingredient. Five-alternative Likert scale was used (I Always agree, I agree very much, I agree sometimes, I rarely agree, I do not agree). The items were scored according to their positive or negative directions. The items of positive direction have been given the scores of (1-5) which reflect the optimistic trait, while the items of negative direction have been given the scores of (5-1) which reflect the pessimistic trait. The total score is ranging (32-10), with an average of (96) the low score reflects the tendency of the person to the pessimism, while the high score indicates the preference of optimism.

Validity

- Face validity: the items of the scales were presented to (10) referees who are specialized in educational and psychological sciences and the degree of their acceptance was (100%).

- The ratio of (27%) which took the highest scores in (PNTS) was chosen and the ratio of (27%) of the forms that took the lowest scores since these ratios were able to get two groups with the largest possible size and maximum variation. Their distributions are close to the natural one. Since the total of the sample of the statistical analysis (construction sample) consisted of (270) forms, the ratio of (27%) consisted of (73) forms for each group. Therefore, the number of forms which undertook the analysis contains (146) forms. The items of the scale were analyzed by using the formula of (T-Test) for two independent samples by using (SPSS) program to check the differences between the two samples, both the highest and lowest and for each item of the scale. The extracted (T value) is considered as an indicator to contrast the item and through balancing the (T value) for each item (with tabular T value) (1.96).

- Person Correlation Co-efficiency has been used to extract the co-relation between each item with the total score of the scale (270). It has been found that all correlation co-efficiencies of the items are significant statistically when it was balanced with the tabular value (0.13) in level of significance (0.05).

Reliability

- A Retest -Test was used. It was applied on a sample of (40) students both males and females (exploratory sample from the original one). They were chosen randomly from the humanistic and pure sciences. After 14 days, the test was repeated on the same sample to check the reliability, which was (0.88). This shows a good reliability according to [10].

Results and interpretations

First, to identify the determiners of thinking of the college students, the scale of thinking (Positive-Negative) was used on a sample of (400) students. By using SPSS programs, the scores of the individuals of the sample of thinking scale were ranging between (162-66). The results of the statistical analysis have shown that the average of the scores of the sample was (118.63) degrees. The standard deviation was (20.38) degrees while the hypothetical average of the scale was (108)

degrees. In order to find out the significance between them, T- test was used for one sample group. The extracted T-Value was (10.436) which is higher than the tabular value (1.98) in significance degrees (0.05) and freedom degrees (399). The results show that the college students enjoy positive patterns of thinking. The researcher attributes this to the idea that the positive thinking reflects positive dimensions of personality. This result is consistent with the theoretical perspectives proposed by (Seligman,1993) which indicates that the positive thinking and behavior are the sources of true happiness. They help the individual to interact positively with others and to be able to set goals and help him to cope with the difficulties raise strength, steadfastness and resistance (Al-A'ser,2005). The researcher also interpreted as a relative stability, which is reflected on his/her way of thinking. In addition, the development of college methods of teaching which focus interaction and exploration. This makes the student look for the information and discuss each other to reach the scientific facts instead of the passive learning. This is consistent with the results of the following studies (Munro, 2004); (Haveren,2004); (Rebecca, 2003); and (Bahheimer,2011). These indicated their results to the tendency of students to the total of positive thinking, while such an outcome opposed the results of studies like (Edmeads,2004); (Morgan et.al,2003); (Anthony,2002) which showed a tendency of college students to negative pattern of thinking in general.

Second: to identify the statistical significant differences of the determiners of thinking of the college students according to the variables: gender (males-females). Specialization(pureSciences-Humanities), level of study (second grade-fourth grade). The researcher has used a triple contrast analysis for each variable separately. The results were as they are clear in Table No.1 below:

Table.1. Tests of between - subjects Effects

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
gender	32.306	1	32.306	0.089
Specialization	373.884	1	373.884	1.035
level of study	133.810	1	133.810	0.370
Specialization*gender	69.367	1	69.367	0.192
level of study*gender	268.808	1	268.808	0.744
level of study*Specialization	45.793	1	45.793	0.127
level of study*Specialization*gender	194.409	1	194.409	0.538
Error	141649.501	392	361.351	
Total	9802944.000	400		
Corrected Total	142658.390	399		

The statistical treatment of table No.1 indicates the following:

The general view of the results of the differences between the determiners of thinking (positive-negative) of college students according to the variables: gender, specialization, and level of study shows that there is no significant differences. This is attributed to the point that they all live within one educational framework and there is no contrast in the scores of determiners of thinking. They all affected by these determiners which pass by the same educational, economic, social, political, and family systems. These might be in the form of opinions, ideas, beliefs, or certain behavioral patterns that describe what the individual should do in the various stances as well as the degree of his/her self-control.

(Carr ,2004) asserts that the most distinctive characteristic of the human being is his strong tendency to the positive thinking. Some studies showed that males are not different from female concerning the determiners of thinking. A study of (Myers,1983) mentioned that individuals (both males and females) usually have unified thought, which are affected by others as a source of information. Thus, the thoughts of the individuals are close to the ideas of others[11].

This result is consistent with the results of the study of (Munro,2004) which has shown the unavailability of differences between the patterns of thinking (Negative-Positive) according to the variables of gender, specialization and level of study. He attributed the reason to the idea that the students, regardless their gender, specialization, or level of study, invest their time in learning thinking and professing its positive skills. (Haveren,2004) mentioned the same thing. On the other hand, (Al-Lail,1993):(Al-Sabahi,1997) concluded that there is a difference in the determiners of thinking according to the gender to the females.

Third: to identify the traits of optimistic- pessimistic personality of college students. A scale of the two traits of personality was used on a sample of (400) college students both males and females. By using SPSS program, it concluded that the scores of the individuals of the sample ranged between (144-76). The results of the statistical analysis that the average of the scores was (109.232) degrees, and the standard deviation was (12943) degrees, while the hypothetical average of the scale was (96) degrees. According to these, the number of optimists was (338) male and female students who compose (84%) of the sample, while the number of pessimistic students was (62) students who compose (15.5%). In order to identify the significance of the difference between them, a T-test was used on one sample group. The extracted T-value was (20.447) degrees which was higher than the tabular value which was (1.98) in significance (0.05), and freedom degree (399). The results have shown that the number of optimist members of the sample was (338) while the pessimists were (62). According to this result, we find that the optimist students are larger in number. The optimist people expect positive things more than the real ones and they expect the negative things to be happened less than the reality. This could lead to unexpected results, which might offer them some danger. This what did (Anderson,1992) mention. The nature of the students' ages, which extend between (19-25) years, is considered as the stage of building the personality, independency, ambition, and social maturity. In addition, the academic stage of the sample, which represents the stage of habituating the

individual to the future and on its bases the future, would be identified. This would motivate optimism within themselves. Moreover, having relax psyche and body, they would have relative stability and reassurance. Usually, college stage is characterized as being the stage of social intimacy and directing the behavior toward the future. This would widen the social relations of the individual and as a result, s/he will expect the better for the future (optimism).The spread of optimism among college students might be due to their expectation that the social, academic, medical, and psychological situations get better status due to the rapid change in the political circumstances in Iraq.

(Norem& Contor,1986) assert that pessimism is a personal readiness or orientation of an individual that make him/her aware of the things around him/her in a negative way. This then would be directed negatively toward him/herself in both the present and future. The researcher noticed that some students are pessimists because of the social circumstances, and the sense of oppression, injustice, and poverty as well as the disability to change these circumstances. This made them feel the loss of hope, despair and submission to others. These might lead them to depression and then the individual would lose the ability of initiation and creation. Therefore, s/he would not want to change the reality especially that many people expected that after the events of (2003) in Iraq as having stability, safety and luxury, but they faced much more violence, chaos, and displacement as well as the absence of law and insecurity etc. all of these led many people to be pessimists and negative. Such result is consistent with the theory of Shire & Carper who believe that pessimism and optimism are personal traits that tare relatively stable and could be changed with the stances and events that the individual face as well his/her expectations for the future. This is totally in line with our present in which we live.

Fourth: To identify the differences between the two traits of personality (pessimistic- optimistic) of college students according to the variables:gender, specialization, and the level of the study, the researcher has used the triple variation analysis for each variable separately. The results were as they are clear in table No.2 below:

Table.2.Tests of between - subjects Effects

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
gender	50.684	1	50.684	0.207
Specialization	258.782	1	258.782	1.057
level of study	346.577	1	346.577	1.415
Specialization*gender	0.2641	1	0.2641	0.001
level of study*gender	365.032	1	365.032	1.490
level of study*Specialization	134.670	1	134.670	0.550
level of study*Specialization*gender	229.409	1	229.409	0.937
Error	96007.129	392	244.916	
Total	6292732.000	400		
Corrected Total	97113.190	399		

Through observing table No.2, the results do not show any differences in the scores of the two traits of personality for the college students for both sexes, the specialization, and level of the study. This indicates that the students feel certain degree of optimism rather than pessimism although they suffer from the social, economic, and political pressures. This also indicates that they have hard and strong personalities. Despite the surrounding circumstances, the hope is still there. This might be attributed to idea that they have the same ages or because of the similarity of the academic life for the subjects of the sample. This is totally or partially consistent with (Hargens& Kelly,1994; Dor othy,1994; Morrison & others,1991), while it is inconsistent with (Edward, 1996; Bennett, 1993; Kolotkin,1994; Koizumi,1995; Seligman,1994).

Fifth: to explore the nature of the relationship between the determiners of thinking and the traits of personality as well as the extent of contribution of the determiners in the two traits for the college students. To do this, the researcher has used a statistical mean represented by the simple regression. After calculating the Pearson correlation co-efficiency, and then choosing the statistically variable signifier, which contributes in the personal traits. The researcher has found that the variable (determiners of thinking) contributes in the traits of personality. On the other hand, the results of Pearson correlation co-efficiency between the variables (the determiners of thinking and the traits of personality) have shown that there is a statistical significant relationship between them as the value of their correlation co-efficiency was (0.99) degrees. Through converting the value of correlation co-efficiency into a T-value, it showed that it is significant as the calculated T-value was (24.347) which is bigger than the tabular T-value in (410) degrees of freedom, and the level of significance (0.00), that is (1.96). This indicates that there is a statistical significant correlation. On the other hand, the value of the total co-efficiency of determination (0.98) R² degrees, while the value of the debugger co-efficiency of determination (0.98) R². These were subjected to regression analysis equation.It appeared that the ratio of alpha calculated equal to (19604.69), which is greater than the value of the ratio of alpha tabular (2.995), and the degree of freedom (1-392). These are statistically significant at the level of significance (0.00), as shown in the table No.3:

Table.3. Regression contrast analysis

S.V	S.S	D.F	M.S	F	SIG	R ²
Regression	65511.4	1	65511.413	19604.6	0.000	0.980
Error	1329.96	398	3.342			
Total	66841.3	399	-			

The transaction values of the two variables were converted in order to identify the relative contribution of the thinking determiners and their standard error to the standardized regression co-efficiency (Beta) which is correspondent to each variable. Through these, it is possible to identify which one of the determiners of thinking and the traits of personality have bigger influence. The results of regression analysis have shown that the variable of the determiners of thinking has a big contribution in its influence on the traits of personality of the college students since the value of the co-efficiency determination was (0.980). This prove that the determiners of thinking demonstrate (98%) of the variation in the degrees of the traits of personality. This is a high effect than the explained variation by the effect of the variable of the determiners of thinking in the traits of personality of the college students. The Beta value for the variable of the determiners of thinking was (34.651). In order to know its significance statistically, its T-value was (64.115) degrees which is statistically significant at level of significance (0.00). On the other hand, the Beta value of the variable of the traits of personality was (0.629) degrees and its T-value was (140.017) degrees which is significant at level of significance (0.00). this indicates that the variable of the determiners of thinking contributes in (98%) of the effect in the degrees of the variable of the traits of personality. The remaining (2%) is attributed to other elements. Generally, the thinking of the individual is affected by the stance according to the degree of positivity and negativity. As much, the thinking of the student is positive, as the trait of optimism is available and vice versa. The optimistic personality expresses the owning of positive expectations toward the outside world. The optimism is a defending mechanism against depression, failure, and disappointment. On the contrary, pessimism expresses the owning of negative ideas towards the outside world and this leads to a monotonous boring life filled with carelessness, isolation, and unhappiness (Goleman, 1995). Thus, the positive ideas contribute in building the optimistic personality. The optimists focus on the positive dimensions when they give their judgments. They tend to have wide view about the positive aspects and epitomize the negative ones. Moreover, they are successful people in general specially that the successful people tend to full themselves with the aspects of success through starting by hope and optimism. Thus, it is hypnotized that the students form the early beginning of their lives look for good basis to build his personality on. Through these bases, they would deal positively and negatively in certain degree with everything around them. The normal person deals usually wisely and patiently. Accordingly, as much the students think in such way as this leads to be optimistic and vice versa. On the other hand, the negative thinking is highly related with the pessimistic personality, which usually suffers from the deterioration of health and the increase of morbidity such as depression, and mental disorder. Psychological and educational studies mentioned that the psychological and mental disorders are not the results of the difficult situations; rather, they are the result of pessimism and despair that he feel toward these situations. This indicates that such individuals look negatively toward their lives and feel disputed form inside (Johnson, 2002; Jbeard,2003; Frank, 2004; Whyte, 2004).

Recommendations

- Emphasize the role of social counselors in the colleges in order to clarify the right educational techniques as well as the methods of dealing with the students, which have a great impact on proper planning for the future in line with the present reality.
- The universities should provide counseling centers to supervise, and guide the students educationally and psychologically as well as helping them to get rid of their social, psychological and emotional problems, which lead to the negative thinking that is filled with frustration, depression, and intolerance.
- Instill the spirit of optimism among the students through the Educational syllabus
- The media should broadcast counseling programs that motivate the students to be optimists, inform them about their future to make their expectations more positive, and activate their abilities in dealing with the daily events.
- The parents should know the various features and traits of their children's personalities to help them to seek change for their lives have much more understanding for the problems that they face, and raise them well.

Suggestions for further studies

- Conduct studies to detect the extent of pessimism and its relationship with the educational and psychological problems.
- Conduct comparative study between the determiners of thinking (positive –negative) of the students who have the traits of the personality (optimistic-pessimistic) among the Iraqi Universities.
- Conduct some studies to investigate the traits of personality (optimistic-pessimistic) and their relations with the capabilities of having hobbies.

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